

Effect of Temperature on the Rate of Coagulation of Thorium oxide and Ceric oxide hydrosols

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The effect of temperature on the rate of coagulation of positively charged thorium oxide and ceric oxide hydrosols in presence of KCl and KBr has been studied. An equation relating the time of coagulation and temperature based on the theory of stability of colloids has been derived and the results have been interpreted quantitatively in that framework. It has been shown that the maximum value of the potential energy barrier for the coagulation of colloids can be calculated approximately by the use of this method.

It has been observed that rise of temperature often hastens the coagulation of colloids. Lachs and Goldbery¹ have studied the coagulation of gold sol at different temperatures and obtained a straight line by plotting the time t_c of coagulation against the ratio η/T , where η =viscosity of the medium and T =absolute temperature. The influence of temperature on the slow coagulation of copper oxide sol has been studied by the Freundlich and Bose² who also have obtained straight line by plotting t_c against η/T .

Recently, the effect of temperature on the coagulation of sols is engaging fresh attention. Kherin and Chai-Kavskaya³ have studied theoretically the effect of temperature on S-sol. In a number of publications Ghosh & coworkers⁴ have studied different sols using an equation of the Arrhenius type

$$\log t_c = \frac{E}{2.303 RT} - \log K P Z$$

where, E is the activation energy, K is a constant, P is a steric factor and Z is the collision frequency.

Since the coagulation of a colloid involves no chemical reaction, the interpretation offered by Ghosh and coworkers does not appear quite logical. In the present communication, the effect of temperature on the coagulation of thorium oxide and ceric oxide hydrosols has been studied and an attempt has been made to interpret the results with the help of an equation relating time of coagulation and temperature based on the theory of stability of colloids developed by Fuchs⁵, Derjaguin⁶ and Overbeek⁷.

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6. B. Derjaguin, *Trans. Farad Soc.*, 1940, **36**, 703.
7. E. J. W. Verwey and J. Th Overbeek, "Theory of the stability of lyophobic colloid" *Elv. Pub. Co., Amster.* (1968), p. 164.

EXPERIMENTAL

(a) *Preparation of the sols*: Positively charged thorium oxide hydrosol has been prepared by the method of Muller⁸ with a slight modification. 20 gms of thorium nitrate was dissolved in 400 c.c. of distilled water, at 70-80°C, followed by dropwise addition of concentrated NH₃ with constant stirring until further addition of ammonia gave a permanent precipitate. Three litres of white and turbid sol obtained in this way was dialysed against distilled water in cellophane bags for about a month when it became almost transparent with a bluish tinge. It was then stored in a jena flask and allowed to age for one month. Specific conductivity at 25°C = 1.27×10^{-4} mho Cm⁻¹, and pH = 3.2.

Positively charged ceric oxide hydrosol was prepared by the method of Blitz⁹. 5% solution of pure ceric ammonium nitrate was allowed to stand for a week in a jena glass bottle when it became turbid and the colour changed from the original reddish orange to more or less greenish yellow. The solution was electro-dialysed for 20 hours and then dialysed for 20 days against distilled water. The resulting solution was stored in a stoppered jena bottle for about a fortnight for ageing. Its specific conductance at 25°C was 1.084×10^{-4} mho Cm⁻¹, and pH = 4.30.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

(b) *Determination of rate of coagulation*: For ThO₂ sol, the change in optical density was followed with Klett-Sommerson Photoelectric Colorimeter. A 42 blue filter in the spectral range of 400-665m was used. Two clear and dry Klett tubes made of glass were taken. In one of them 2 c.c. of the ThO₂ sol and in the other an equal volume of electrolyte solution were taken and these two were placed in a thermostat to attain the desired temperature. When the desired temperature was reached, the electrolyte solution was added to the sol and the mixture poured back into the original test tube which contained the electrolyte solution. After mixing, the test tube containing the mixture was placed in the bath quickly. Now and then it was taken out for a very short time and the optical density noted. Using the same concentration of electrolyte the experiment was repeated at different temperatures. Since CeO₂ hydrosol has a strong absorption in the range 400-465 m, a different technique was followed. In six clean, dry test tubes, 2 c.c. of sol and in another 6 tubes an equal volume of electrolyte solutions were taken and they were placed in a

8. A. Muller, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 2857.9. W. Blitz, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 4431; *Z. anorg. chem.*, 1927, 96, 108.

thermostat at the temperatures required. When they attained the desired temperature, mixing was effected as described before in the case of ThO_2 sol and the tubes containing the mixtures were put in the bath quickly. From time to time, one of the test tubes were taken out, centrifuged for 2 minutes at 2500 r.p.m. and the supernatant solution was examined for just transparency. The time t_s required to attain a definite stage of coagulation determined by the aforesaid methods has been found to be reproducible within 8 percent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The optical density of ThO_2 sol has been plotted against time. The interval of time required to attain a given optical density is noted. It is assumed that a given optical density corresponds to a definite stage of coagulation. For ThO_2 the experiments were carried out at 12°, 20°, 28° and 34.5°C, and for CeO_2 sol at 15°, 25°, 37° and 50°C. Electrolytes used were KCl (0.128 M and 0.01040 M) and KBr (0.01327 M).

The stability ratio (W) of a colloid defined as the ratio of the limiting rate of rapid coagulation to the rate of slow coagulation is given by

$$W = 2 \int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-V/kT}}{e} \frac{ds}{s^2}$$

where s stands for R/a , R being the distance between the centres of the two particles each of radius a . Overbeek and coworkers⁷ have pointed out that the value of W may to a good approximation, be represented by

$$W = \frac{1}{2ka} e^{V_{\max}/kT}$$

where $V_{\max}$ = maximum in the potential energy curve

$$\text{or } \log W = \frac{V_{\max}}{kT} - \log 2ka$$

where ka represents the ratio of the particle radius, a , to the thickness of the double layer $1/k$.

Again, $W = \frac{t_s}{t}$, where t_s = time for slow coagulation and t = characteristic time for rapid coagulation.

Therefore, $\log t_s = \log t + \log W$

$$= \log t + \frac{V_{\max}}{2.303kT} - \log 2ka.$$

But, t , the characteristic time of rapid coagulation is given by

$$t = \frac{3\eta}{4kTn}$$

where η is the viscosity of the liquid and n the number of colloidal particles per ml.

It has been shown by Frenkel¹⁰ that the viscosity of liquid varies with temperature according to the equation

$$\eta = Ake^{\frac{E}{kT}}$$

where A is a constant, E the energy of activation and the other terms have the same significance as stated before.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Therefore, } \log t_s &= \log \frac{3A}{4n} + \frac{1}{2.303} \left[\frac{E}{kT} + \frac{V_{\max}}{kT} \right] - \log 2ka \\ &= \frac{E + V_{\max}}{2.303kT} + B \\ &= \frac{N(E + V_{\max})}{2.303kT} + B \quad \dots \quad (1) \end{aligned}$$

where, $B = \log \frac{3A}{8nk_a} = \text{a constant}$, since variation of k involving product of dielectric constant and temperature within the range of temperature investigated is small. Thus a plot of $\log t_s$ against $1/T$ should be a straight line.

FIG. 3

The logarithm of time required to attain a given optical density is plotted against the temperature for thorium hydroxide sol. This is shown in Fig. 1. Similarly the log of time required to coagulate CeO_2 solution with KCl and KBr has been plotted against $1/T$. This is shown in Figs. 2 and 3. All the plots have yielded straight lines in accordance

with equation (1). The values of $N V_{\max}$ for ThO_2 hydrosol in presence of 0.128 M KCl is calculated from the slope of the plot. This is equal to 16,390 cal., the value of NE of water being 3.305K. cal/mole¹¹. Similarly for CeO_2 hydrosol, the mean value of $N V_{\max}$ has been found to be 18,330 cal.

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Received, June 5, 1967.